

D6.1 Website and social media accounts

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1 Summary

This project activity aimed to design, develop, and launch a professional website for ArcSolution project (www.arcsolution.eu) and establish social media channels. The website and social media platforms enhance ArcSolution's online presence, engaging potential target audiences and showcasing the project. This report details the key facts and activities and touches on plans.

2 Scope of Work

1. Website Development – Creating an accessible, simple website that effectively communicates ArcSolution's key facts, results and news.
2. Establishment of Social Media Channels—Set up and initial content deployment on major social media platforms (LinkedIn and Facebook) to connect with a broader audience and drive traffic to the website.

2.1 Website Development

- **Domain Acquisition:** Secured the project's website domain, www.arcsolution.eu, to establish a dedicated online presence.
- **Technical Implementation:** An IT technician at Nord University built a foundational website using a WordPress CMS with responsive design templates to ensure accessibility across devices. Basic SEO optimization, including metadata and mobile compatibility, was integrated.
- **Design and Planning:** Team members from WP1 and WP6 collaborated to outline essential design requirements, including brand colours, fonts, and a clean, minimalist layout. At the same time, they created PowerPoint and Word templates with a consistent design to ensure our communication reflects the same visual identity.
- **Content Creation:** Developed content for main pages—Home, Study locations, Participants, About ArcSolution and News section.
- **Testing and Launch:** Conducted usability and performance tests on stationary and mobile devices to address potential issues before the public launch. The website went live on November 5th, 2024.

2.2 Social Media Channels Establishment

- **Planning:** We evaluated potential social media platforms, considering available resources to ensure active management and growth. We decided to focus on a select number of platforms for maximum impact.

- **Account Setup:** Profiles were established on LinkedIn (LI) and Facebook (FB) featuring consistent branding, including logos and descriptions aligned with project identity. Links to the pages:
 - **FB:** <https://www.facebook.com/arcsolutionEU>
 - **LI:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/arcsolution>
- **Initial Content Deployment.** The first posts focus on project-related news and recent activities. Further development of these social media channels, including a strategic approach to communication, is outlined in the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) plan.

2.3 Outcomes and current activities

The new website features a straightforward, streamlined interface with intuitive navigation and professional design, enhancing ArcSolution's credibility. Key project information has been published, and we are now focusing on producing news items to drive traffic to the site.

Since its launch, the associated social media platforms have experienced gradual but steady growth in followers and engagement, with LinkedIn proving particularly effective for reaching industry professionals.

Furthermore, discussions have been held with our sister projects, ILLUQ and ICEBERG, to feature cross-references to each other's projects on our respective websites. We are actively engaging with their content and collaborating on mutual promotion to expand reach and visibility.

3 Next Steps

- Continue to optimize and update the website with new content, case studies, and SEO improvements.
- Expand social media content and engagement activities to increase followers and interaction.
- Establish links between social media channels and the website with new content going live.
- Monitor metrics and adjust strategies to maximize reach and engagement across digital channels.
- Implement ArcSolution Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan to digital channels.
- In the above plan, we will create an action plan with content we are sure will be produced during the project. The action plan will be a live document that we will continuously update and plan our activity.